

1

This man was feeling too tired to do anything. Everything was an effort.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

nothing

little bit

sometimes

a lot

all the time

2

This man felt really worried a lot.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

nothing

little bit

sometimes

a lot

all the time

3

This man felt so sad, nothing could make him feel happy.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

nothing

little bit

sometimes

a lot

all the time

4 This man felt like everything in his life
was no good.
He felt hopeless.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

5 This man felt really jumpy.
He had to move or walk about a lot.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

Notes

1 _____
2 _____
3 _____
4 _____
5 _____

Total _____